

resistance or susceptibility to gall midge or recording midge infestation and parasitization in the field often do not record infestation and parasitization of suppressed galls.

To estimate the proportion of exposed and suppressed galls in the infested hills, 20 random hills of Jaya in the vegetative stage were dissected every 2 weeks for 3 years and 7,541 galls were tested to determine the parasitization percentage in exposed versus suppressed galls.

There was a 4:1 ratio of exposed to suppressed galls (Fig. 1). Parasitization in the suppressed galls was higher during early Apr, May, and Jun, late Jan and Mar, and in Jul (Fig. 2). □

2. Parasitization of galls by *Platygaster oryzae*.

Thaia subrufa (Homoptera:Cicadellidae) occurrence in Karnataka, India

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Thaia leafhoppers are becoming serious pests of cereals, especially rice. *Thaia oryzivora* Ghauri and *T. subrufa* (Motschulsky) cause substantial damage to rice in several Asian countries.

In Feb 1978, *T. subrufa* adults and nymphs were found in large numbers on leaf blades of rice seedlings in summer crop nurseries in Mudigere. Infestation persisted, even on transplanted rice plants, in Mar-Apr 1978 and caused hopperburn symptoms in some plots. Panicle size in affected plots was considerably reduced. Leafhopper populations were so high that 150 to 200 adults were col-

lected in each sweep of a 25-cm diameter insect net. The ratio of males to females ranged from 1:1.20 to 1:2.06 in different months.

Adults and nymphs usually sucked on the leaf undersurface, causing white specks on the upper surface, which often ran into zigzag lines. The specks later turned brown and gave the plants a burnt appearance. When enclosed on rice plants in the laboratory, a single adult damaged a 1-cm² area a day. Preliminary biological observations show that the nymphal period lasts 23-25 days and has 5 instars, and that adults live 33-45 days.

Pest activity in the rice fields has been monitored since 1978. Although found throughout the year, the pest bred actively Oct-May and severely damaged the summer crop. Light trap catches of adults are shown in the table. The pest was also seen on several grass weeds and on finger millet *Eleusine coracana* Gaertn.

Light trap catches of *Thaia subrufa* in Karnataka, India.

Month	Leafhoppers (no.) ^a	
	1981	1982
Jan	577	205
Feb	635	145
Mar	287	59
Apr	175	231
May	92	168
Jun	4	2
Jul	0	2
Aug	-	-
Sep	0	-
Oct	16	3
Nov	164	193
Dec	246	99

^a - = no observation.

Dimethoate, methyl parathion, and quinalphos at 0.05% spray effectively controlled the pest. Leafhopper populations also declined after a heavy rain. □

Effect of nitrogen and plant density on rice stem borer infestation in Western Kenya

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A survey of rice ecosystems in Kenya showed that rice farmers grow rice in low-fertility swamps at high plant density (about 1 million hills/ha at 10- × 10-cm

spacing) because they believe higher plant populations will produce higher yields.

We studied the effect of plant density and fertility on insect infestation in field trials at Mbita Point, in western Kenya, under swampy lowland conditions. Sindano, a traditional rice variety, was grown on black cotton soil (saline phase, gleyic solonetz) composed of 40% sand, 14% silt, and 46% clay. Rice was planted at 10- × 20- and 20- × 20-cm spacing for populations of 500,000 and 250,000 hills/ha. Nitrogen was applied at

0,60, and 120 kg/ha at land preparation with 30 kg P and 50 kg K/ha. The predominant rice insect was stem borer. No disease was observed.

Results showed that stem borer damage was the same for crops at different plant densities, except at 120 kg N/ha. Deadhearts were caused by *Diopsis* spp. and whiteheads by *Sesamia calamistis*.

Infestation by combined *S. calamistis* and *Maliarpha separattella* did not differ among treatments (see table), but percentage of empty grains was significant.